
Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

Cynthia V. Yañez

DepEd- Division of Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines

ABSTRACT: The primary purpose of the study was to develop a structural model for school heads' performance in terms of their leadership skills, behaviors, and practices. The study used descriptive correlational and causal research designs as well as patterned and modified survey instruments. Three hundred ninety-nine (399) teachers from the Division of Cagayan de Oro City were the respondents using a sampling procedure. The data were described through descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation. The Pearson-Product Moment Correlation Coefficients identified the interrelationship between the variables. The amount of influence of the independent variables on the dependent variables for school heads' performance was established using multiple regression. The effects of the variables tested were determined using path analysis. It is revealed in the findings of the study that school heads' level of leadership skills is highly proficient as perceived by the teachers. School heads showed high proficiency in communication skills which got the highest mean value in terms of school heads' level of leadership skills. School heads' level of leadership behaviors is moderately proficient and proficiency level in leadership behaviors in terms of intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, and idealized influencer School heads have a moderate. There is a significant relationship between the performance of school heads and leadership skills, behaviors, and practices. Leadership practices focusing on teaching and learning, managing school operations and resources and leadership behaviors on idealized influence and inspirational motivation are the four variables that best predict the performance of school heads. Structural Model 5 is the best fit model for the performance of school heads anchored in leadership practices supported by leadership skills.

KEYWORDS: intellectual simulation, individualized consideration, skills, behaviors, practices

I. INTRODUCTION

School is one of the most essential units in society. It is where children learn the basics of reading and writing next to home. Their knowledge, skills and full potential are honed in the school with the help and guidance of the teachers and the supervision of the school heads. School heads play a vital and crucial role in school. They are the prime movers in the implementation of programs and projects in the Department of Education. The success of the school depends on the performance of the school heads. However, school leaders are facing various challenges in the field of education nowadays.

The *Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA, 2018)* of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) where the Philippines joined for the first time and the results showed that Philippines ranked last among the 79 participating countries and economies in reading and second to the last in science and mathematics (*World Bank, 2020*).

The quality of education in the country was put under the spotlight in 2019 following the results of both local and international assessments on students' performance which highlighted the low performance of Filipino learners (Malipot, 2019). Former Education Briones (2020) said that the performance of Filipino students in large scale assessment - which is the National Achievement Test (NAT) - "gravitates towards the low proficiency levels" especially in Science, Math, and English. NAT is administered for Grade 6, Grade 10, and Grade 12 students.

While the results were heartbreaking and discouraging, the Department of Education sector considers this as a challenge, and this will serve as a wake-up call to all education leaders, teachers, and stakeholders to work together to achieve one common goal: quality education for all learners.

Therefore, school heads as important key people in the educational process take this challenge. His leadership acumen is very vital in leading and managing a school. Research has shown that effective school leadership is strongly associated with improved student achievement. According to Upendo (2020), a good leader should make sure that he or she initiates

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

stakeholder inclusively in all key issues and in making decisions. In some situations, the leader's informed views may be pushed through in what may seem like force especially when subordinates seem not interested or committed enough. Effective school leadership leads to good school productivity, that is good performance of students in national examinations.

Nowadays, there are many new breeds of school heads assigned in the schools. Although they undergone the process of promotion on merit and fitness and had attended several trainings and seminars yet, they still need to deepen their understanding and awareness on their kind of leadership skills, behaviors, and practices to answer the needs of the clientele in the school where they are assigned. It is also important that the school heads would consider the voice of the teachers on how they value and assess the presence of the school heads in the school because they will be working together in achieving the goals, mission & vision of the department.

According to D.O 24 s. 2020, School heads as stewards of schools play a crucial role in ensuring an enabling and supportive environment for effective teaching and learning. Through their quality leadership and management, the Department of Education (DepEd) can develop quality teachers and "holistic learners who are steeped in values, equipped with 21st century skills and be able to propel the country to development and progress (D.O no.42 s. 2017). Teacher quality is vital in raising learner achievement. However, teachers alone cannot bring about substantive changes without effective leadership.

The Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) as stipulated in D.O. 24. S. 2020 introduces the continuum of professional practices that supports school heads to pursue career progression. The PPSSH framework depicts the synergy between maximizing school effectiveness and ensuring people effectiveness through a broad sphere of instructional and administrative practice stipulated in the five domains; 1. Leading strategically, 2. Managing School Operations and Resources, 3. Focusing on Teaching and Learning, 4. Developing Self and Others and 5. Building Connections.

With this, the Department of Education (DepEd) has strengthened its mandate on school heads and teachers' professional development while ensuring the full awareness of school heads on their leadership skills, practices and behaviors which are significant in achieving quality performance in school.

This study hopefully will come up with the best remedies that may be found effective by the school heads in facing challenges. Through structural equation modelling of the leadership skills, behaviors, and practices on the performance of school heads would achieve desired learning.

This study is anchored on Contemporary Leadership Theory by Greenleaf (1990). Contemporary theory is a group of modern literary approaches to leadership. Contemporary leaders use personal influence to develop and inspire people to achieve organizational goals. This theory considers that leadership skills are present in every individual. The four vital leadership skills are Communication Skills, Interpersonal Skills, Problem Solving/ Decision making skills and Delegation / Managing work skills.

Another theory that this study is anchored is on Transformational Leadership theory of Mac Gregor Burns (1978). It is a theory of leadership where a leader works with teams or followers beyond their immediate self-interests to identify needed change, creating a vision to guide the change through influence, inspiration, and executing the change in tandem with committed members of a group. It is a relatively new approach to leadership that focuses on how leaders can create valuable and positive change in their followers. The four key behaviors of transformational leadership are idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration.

The theory on Contingency Theory of leadership by Fiedler (1964) is also another theory that this study is anchored. It states that people become leaders because of their qualities and various situational factors, and the interactions between group members and the leader. This model explains the relationship between leadership style and the favorableness of a situation. To cultivate such an environment, school heads must navigate and promote collaboration across the often-complex network of stakeholders: education authorities, teachers, students, parents, and local communities.

Further, this study is anchored on the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads' (PPSSH) Framework (D.O #24 s. 2020) which depicts the synergy between maximizing school effectiveness and ensuring people effectiveness through a broad sphere of instructional and administrative practices stipulated in the five domains. The placement of learner at the center of the framework emphasizes the important role of school heads for the improvement of learner achievement.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study employed descriptive correlational design and causal comparative research designs. Mc Combes (2020) explains that descriptive research aims to describe a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically and can use a wide research method to investigate one or more variables. She further explains correlational research is a type of descriptive research that measures the relationship between the variables. In comparison, causal research, as cited by Bhasin (2020) is to determine the relationship between a cause and effect. It is also known as explanatory research. Other confounding variables that may influence the results are kept constant while applying statistical procedures to create the data to produce accurate output.

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

The nature of causal research is very complicated as a researcher can never be sure that no other hidden variable will influence the causal relationship between two variables.

The descriptive-correlational study design is helpful when examining the associations between the same variables in two populations or between the same variables in two groups of people (Curtis et al., 2016). Problems 5 to 6 necessitated this type of design. The last problem was answered by Causal Comparative design using Structural Equation Modelling. A method to study cause-and-effect interactions among variables in diverse disciplines is structural equation modeling (SEM). The linear relationship between latent and observable variables is also found using SEM. Several visible factors can serve as substitutes for these latent variables. A hypothesized model showing directional and non-directional correlations between latent and observable variables is built using SEM. SEM is frequently employed to decide whether a model must consider covariation and variation of latent and visible factors (Karakaya-Ozyer & Aksu-Dunya, 2018) as mentioned by Digamon, 2023. The survey method was used to gather data to determine the level of leadership skills, behaviors, and practices on the performance of the school heads.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problem 1. What is the level of leadership skills among the school heads as perceived by the teachers in terms of the ff:

- 1.1 Communication skill;
- 1.2 Interpersonal skill;
- 1.3 Problem-solving / Decision-making skills;
- 1.4 Delegation /Managing work skills?

Table 1. Summary of School Heads' Level of Leadership Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
Communication skill	4.5644	.53372	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Interpersonal skill	4.5624	.62421	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Problem-solving / Decision-making skills	4.5228	.66170	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Delegation/ Managing work skills	4.5293	.60907	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Overall Mean	4.55	.566	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency

Legend: 4:50-5.00 High Proficiency 3.50-4.49 Moderate Proficiency 2.50-3.49 Low Proficiency
1.50-2:49 Very Low Proficiency 1.00-1.49 No Proficiency

Table 1 summarizes the school heads' level of leadership skills in terms of communication skill, interpersonal skill, problem-solving/ decision-making skills, and delegation/ managing work skills. Overall data show that the level of school heads leadership skill was highly proficient, as indicated by the overall mean value of 4.55 (SD=0.566) and a description of strongly agree. The results implied that school heads nowadays are already aware of their duties, responsibilities, and functions as a school leader. Their capabilities and skills in leading and managing a school can be seen and observed by the teachers in school. With the indicators presented above, Communication skill got the highest mean value of 4.564. School heads are equipped with necessary skill in terms of communicating with the teachers and other stakeholders.

While Problem-solving/ Decision making skill got the lowest mean value of 4.522 and a standard deviation of 0.661. According to Patuawa (2022) reducing inequity is the moral imperative confronting today's educational leaders. Anent to reducing inequity is leaders' ability to solve the school-based problems that contribute to it, while building the positive and trusting professional relationships required for teachers to commit for improvement.

Problem 2. What is the level of transformational leadership behaviors among the school heads as perceived by their teachers in terms of the ff:

- 2.1 Intellectual stimulation;
- 2.2 Individualized consideration;
- 2.3 Inspirational motivation; and
- 2.4 Idealized Influence?

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

Table 2. Summary of School Heads' Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviors

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
Intellectual stimulation	4.3801	.65401	Moderately Agree	Moderate Proficiency
Individualized consideration	4.4620	.69024	Moderately Agree	Moderate Proficiency
Inspirational motivation	4.5255	.66108	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Idealized influencer	4.4612	.74317	Moderately Agree	Moderate Proficiency
Overall Mean	4.46	.641	Moderately Agree	Moderate Proficiency

Legend: 4:50-5.00 High Proficiency 3.50-4.49 Moderate Proficiency 2.50-3.49 Low Proficiency
1.50-2:49 Very Low Proficiency 1.00-1.49 No Proficiency

Table 2 summarizes the school heads level of transformational leadership behaviors. The overall result showed that the school heads have a moderate proficiency level as revealed by the mean value of 4.46 and standard deviation of 0.641 and a qualitative description of moderately agree. The result demonstrates that the school heads have shown appropriate and favorable leadership behaviors toward the teachers and other school personnel. Effective school leaders, a healthy atmosphere in schools, and positive attitudes in teachers are generally seen to have a direct or indirect impact on school performance and student accomplishment (Hallinger & Heck, 1998; Kruger, Witziers, & Slegers, 2007; Witziers, Bosker, & Kruger, 2003) as mentioned by Beceri (2022).

Inspirational motivation got the highest mean value of 4.525 (SD=0.661) with a qualitative description of Strongly agree. School heads had manifested that they did their best to inspire and motivate their teachers to work efficiently and effectively in school. Their presence being a leader motivates the teachers to do their tasks and responsibilities especially in curriculum and instruction. On the other hand, Intellectual stimulation got the lowest mean value of 4.380 (SD=0.654) with a qualitative description of moderately agree having a moderate proficiency level. It shows that the school heads are moderately proficient in terms of stimulating the intellectual capacity and potential of the teachers. They need to provide activities and actions that would guide and help the teachers in creating, thinking and innovating new ways that would help solve their problems in the classrooms and thus make their works efficient and effective.

Problem 3. What is the level of leadership practices among the school heads as perceived by their teachers in terms of the ff. domains:

- 3.1.1 Leading Strategically;
- 3.1.2 Managing School Operations and Resources;
- 3.1.3 Focusing on Teaching and Learning;
- 3.1.4 Developing Self and Others; and
- 3.1.5 Building Connections?

Table 3. Summary of School Heads' Level of Leadership Practices.

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
Leading strategically	4.6470	.50975	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Managing school operations and resources.	4.6219	.58750	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Focusing on teaching and learning.	4.6133	.56569	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Developing self and others	4.6344	.53550	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Building connections.	4.6409	.54908	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Overall Mean	4.63	.518	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency

Legend: 4:50-5.00 High Proficiency 3.50-4.49 Moderate Proficiency 2.50-3.49 Low Proficiency
1.50-2:49 Very Low Proficiency 1.00-1.49 No Proficiency

Table 3 summarizes the school heads' level of leadership practices. School heads have shown high proficiency in all indicators of level of leadership practices with an overall mean value of 4.63 and standard deviation of 0.518 with qualitative description of strongly agree. This implied that the teachers as respondents of the study have seen the school heads demonstrated and displayed these areas of leadership practices every day during the carrying -out of their duties and responsibilities. In the study

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

of Lasno, et. al (2019), it was found out that the school principal invites community leaders, government elements, both the Education Office and the Environmental Service to discuss the activities that were carried out in meetings to plan school activities.

On the other hand, indicator 3 “focusing on teaching and learning got the lowest mean value of 4.613 and a standard deviation of 0.535 with a qualitative description of strongly agree. According to the study findings of Ampofo, et. al (2019), school heads visit and supervise teaching in the classroom. They monitored the instructional delivery of their teachers to offer technical assistance. The monitoring of teachers’ instructional delivery by school heads ties in with the findings of Malunda, Onen, Musaazi and Oonyu (2016) cited by Oco (2022) on instructional supervision and the pedagogical practices of secondary school teachers in Uganda which revealed that school heads supervision of lesson delivery through classroom observations has statistically significant effect on the pedagogical practices of teachers in public secondary schools in Uganda. Out of the 5 indicators, indicator 3 “focusing on teaching and learning” got the lowest mean, it shows that school heads are more focused on the other tasks and areas of concerns on their daily functions than giving more of their significant times and effort on monitoring and observing the teaching and learning process in school. As a school head, he or she must see to it that his main function in leading a school is to ensure that students learn significantly in schools and that teachers teach effectively and efficiently. He needs to focus on monitoring and providing technical assistance on teaching and learning aspect.

Problem 4. What is the Level of Performance of School Heads?

Table 4 shows the level of performance of school heads as perceived by the teachers. Overall, teachers strongly agreed that school heads have performed well in their work as school leaders, as manifested by an over-all mean of 4.54 and standard deviation of 0.559 with an interpretation of High proficiency. The results agree that school heads ensured the maximum utilization of available monitoring and evaluation processes and tools to promote learner achievement. In fact, various assessment, monitoring and evaluation tools were made available in LRMDs both offline and online just to ensure that learners’ progress are better monitored. Some of these tools are the Division-wide quarterly tests made and validated by the instructional supervisors, reading and numeracy skills tools such as ASER, PHIL-IRI and other available skill inventory and assessment tools. School heads indeed are highly proficient in the carrying out of their functions.

Table 4. School Heads’ Level of Performance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
1. Ensured the communication to the wider community of the developed, implemented, and reviewed school plans, projects, and policies which are aligned with the vision, mission, and core values.	4.53	.637	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
2. Implemented programs in the school that support the development of the learners	4.58	.608	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
3. Utilized available monitoring and evaluation processes and tools to promote learner achievement	4.59	.627	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
4. Managed school data and information using technology, including ICT, to ensure efficient and effective school operations	4.58	.596	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
5. Managed school facilities and equipment in adherence to policies, guidelines, and issuances on acquisition, recording, utilization, repair, and maintenance, storage, and disposal	4.47	.693	Moderately Agree	Moderate Proficiency
6. Managed staffing such as teaching load distribution and grade level and subject area assignment in adherence to laws, policies, guidelines, and issuances based on the needs of the school.	4.58	.621	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
7. Assisted teachers in the review, contextualization, and implementation of learning standards to make the curriculum relevant for learners.	4.52	.649	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
8. Provided Technical Assistance to teachers on teaching standards and pedagogies within and across learning areas on the different learning modalities to improve their teaching practice.	4.53	.641	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
9. Managed a learner-friendly, inclusive, and healthy environment	4.59	.631	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

10. Implemented professional development initiatives to enhance the strengths and address the performance gaps among school personnel	4.52	.657	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
11. Provided opportunities to individuals and teams in performing leadership roles and responsibilities.	4.53	.668	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
12. Implemented a school rewards system to recognize and motivate learners, school personnel and other stakeholders for exemplary performance and/or continues support	4.42	.718	Moderately Agree	Moderate Proficiency
13. Built constructive relationships with authorities, colleagues, parents, and other stakeholders to foster an enabling and supportive environment for learners	4.51	.683	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
14. Managed school organizations, such as learner organizations, faculty clubs and parent-teacher associations, by applying relevant policies and guidelines to support the attainment of institutional goals	4.54	.664	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
15. Communicated effectively in speaking and in writing to teachers, learners, parents, and other stakeholders, through positive use of communication platforms, to facilitate information sharing, collaboration, and support	4.54	.674	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency
Overall Mean	4.54	.559	Strongly Agree	High Proficiency

Legend: 4:50-5.00 High Proficiency 3.50-4.49 Moderate Proficiency 2.50-3.49 Low Proficiency
1.50-2.49 Very Low Proficiency 1.00-1.49 No Proficiency

This is supported by the study of Bantolo, et. al (2021) which states that competencies of school heads in terms of school leadership rated very high were in developing and involving stakeholders, in the drafting of the school vision, mission, goals and objectives for co-ownership. And, in addressing the causes of problems and providing solutions, establishing, and utilizing data-based strategic planning, coordinating concerned staff and stakeholders on the planning and implementation of programs and projects. Further, in assisting the teachers to identify their strengths and weaknesses and be able to find solutions and interventions in addressing the weaknesses. School heads must then be a good team player to be able to play harmoniously with the teachers, parents, and stakeholders to win in whatever school projects and plans they would play. Geleta (2015) states that the principal as instructional leader actively promotes more effective practices in the teaching and learning processes and recognizing instructional priorities rather than by serving as a school manager. Further it mentioned that the principals need to have the competence to create a shared vision and clear goals for their schools and ensure continuous progress toward achieving the goals; support the implementation of high-quality standards-based instruction that results in higher levels of achievement for all students. Nyamubi (2021) study reveals that heads of schools assist teachers in refining their competencies essential for better teaching and disciplining students. In this regard, heads of schools who are efficient in supervision endow with help in assisting teachers in preparing lesson plans and lesson notes, instructional teaching material and provide clear objectives.

On the contrary, indicator 12 “Implemented a school rewards system to recognize and motivate learners, school personnel and other stakeholders for exemplary performance and/or continues support” got the lowest mean value of 4.42 and a standard deviation of 0.718 with a qualitative description of moderately agree. It shows that school heads still lack the initiative of giving rewards and recognizing the efforts of learners, teachers, and other school personnel to whatever exemplary performances they rendered which give honor and pride to the school. Gyansah, et. al (2020) study concludes that the following practices that constituted indicators of the inspirational motivation leadership behaviour were part of the leadership behaviors of heads of SHS in the Kumasi metropolis, such as: the school heads recognized and celebrated the schools’ academic accomplishments and acknowledged failures, they enthusiastically spoke about the academic objectives of the school that needed to be achieved, ensured there was team work to promote teaching and learning, had confidence that staff and students will accomplish challenging academic goals, consulted students’ representatives on academic issues, ensured his actions and deeds were understood and exhibited commitment to the academic goals of the school. Nyamubi (2021) study concludes that there is a strong relationship between heads of schools’ use of inspirational motivation and teachers’ work performance. Heads of schools help teachers to focus on work in promoting teachers’ work performance, using inspirational motivation to encourage them to focus on work by attending in the school and perform well their tasks.

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between the performance of school heads and

- 1.1 leadership skills;
- 1.2 behaviors; and
- 1.3 practices?

The relevance of the association between performance of School heads and leadership skills, behaviors and practices is shown in Table 5. The correlation coefficients, p-values, judgment on the hypothesis at the level of significance of 0.05, and statistical interpretation are all included in the table. The null hypothesis "There is no significant relationship between the performance of school heads and leadership skills; behaviors; and practices" is rejected.

Table 5. Relationship Between the Performance of School Heads' Leadership Skills, Behavior, and Leadership Practices.

	R-VALUE	PROBABILITY	Interpretation
LEADERSHIP SKILLS	.890**	0.000	Highly Significant
Communication Skills	.819**	0.000	Highly Significant
Interpersonal	.861**	0.000	Highly Significant
Problem-solving/Decision Making	.846**	0.000	Highly Significant
Delegation /Managing Work skills	.790**	0.000	Highly Significant
LEADERSHIP BEHAVIORS	.841**	0.000	Highly Significant
Intellectual Stimulation	.752**	0.000	Highly Significant
Individualized Consideration	.776**	0.000	Highly Significant
Inspirational Motivation	.797**	0.000	Highly Significant
Idealized Influencer	.811*	0.000	Highly Significant
LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	.976**	0.000	Highly Significant
Leading strategically	.899**	0.000	Highly Significant
Managing school operations & resources	.926**	0.000	Highly Significant
Focusing on Teaching & learning	.961**	0.000	Highly Significant
Developing Self & Others	.901**	0.000	Highly Significant
Building Connections	.908**	0.000	Highly Significant

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 presents the correlation analysis results of school heads' performance and leadership skills, leadership behavior and leadership practices. The data reveals a statistically highly significant positive correlation between the school heads' leadership skills, behavior, and practices at a 0.01 level (2-tailed). Furthermore, findings revealed a highly significant positive relationship between school heads' performance and leadership practices ($r=0.976$, $p=0.000$), school heads' performance and leadership skills ($r=0.890$, $p=0.000$); and school heads' performance and leadership behavior ($r=0.841$, $p=0.000$). Hence the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between the school heads' performance and leadership skills, behavior, and practices are rejected.

As shown in the table, the relationship between school heads' performance on the area of focusing on teaching and learning got the highest significant correlation of all the variables ($r=0.961$). Further the relationship between the school heads' performance and managing school operations & resources got the second highest correlation value of $r=.926$ and the relationship between school heads' performance and building connections got third highest significant correlation value of $r=0.908$.

On the other hand, the relationship between school heads' performance and intellectual stimulation got the lowest significant correlation value of $r=0.752$ but still highly significant. The results imply that as school heads intellectual stimulation increases their performance also increase. Classroom Observation for Teachers (COT) need to be strengthened to address the needs of the teachers and provide them with significant technical assistance to improve the quality of the delivery of instruction and teaching. It is confirmed in the study of Ampofo (2019) which found that school heads allocated very little time for supervision of lesson planning and delivery of teachers. The study established that school heads' lesson planning supervision ($p=0.043 < .05$)

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

and lesson delivery supervision ($p = .035 < .05$) had a significant influence on teacher's role performance. In addition, teachers' schemes of work and lesson plans are the most vital instructional documents that aid effective instructional delivery. Schemes of work and lesson plans clearly define the structure and content of a course and map out how resources, class activities and assessment strategies will be used to ensure attainment of course objectives (Gakuya, 2013).

Results further show that performance of school heads have significant relationship on their leadership skills, transformational leadership behaviors and leadership practices. All the indicators found in each variable are highly significant to the performance of school heads. Further, it shows that school heads find it necessary to prioritize the task on focusing on teaching and learning. They need to devote most of their time and effort on monitoring the curriculum and instruction, observe and provide the teachers with technical assistance that would help improve their teaching delivery especially the newly hired teachers.

In addition, school heads must give focus and attention also in motivating and stimulating the teachers and colleagues to create and think of innovative ways on how to solve their common problems on poor teaching styles, poor classroom management, problems on non-readers, low academic performance and dropouts, etc. As a leader, he needs to be with the teachers in addressing the issues, concerns and problems of the teachers and learners in the school. He is the stimulus to drive the teachers to think, behave, act and perform with energy and enthusiasm to achieve the goals, vision and mission of the department.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

From the findings drawn in the study, the following are the conclusions:

The school heads' level of leadership skills is highly proficient, which means that school heads nowadays are well-equipped and capacitated with appropriate skills in handling and leading the school system.

The leadership behavior of school heads is moderately proficient, which implies that there is still a need to enhance and improve in the school heads behaviors especially in terms of stimulating, inspiring and influencing the teachers and other colleagues in the school to work with him as a team.

The school heads are highly proficient in their leadership practices, which means that teachers vividly felt and seen the school heads have demonstrated the appropriate practices in managing the school. Focusing on teaching and learning as a leadership practice needs to be improved by the school heads in their daily functions.

Leadership skills, behaviors and practices have contributed to a highly positive significant relationships with the performance of school heads. These imply that the more proficient the school heads in their leadership skills, behaviors, and practices, the higher their performance.

Focusing on teaching and learning, managing school operations and resources, Idealized influence, and inspirational motivation are the four variables that best predict school heads' performance.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are suggested considering the abovementioned findings and conclusions.

Department of Education, Region and Division offices may continually provide training and capacity buildings to school heads for the upgrading and enhancing of their knowledge, skills, and behaviors.

Division Education Program Supervisors and Public Schools District Supervisors may constantly conduct monitoring and evaluation, visitation, and inspection to schools, checking on school heads' needs and weaknesses and providing appropriate technical assistance to school heads that would help them grow and improve.

School heads may continuously engage and participate in seminars, training and workshops for personal and professional growth and development. Also, continue to enroll in post graduate studies, read the latest books and publications and keep abreast with information relative to new trends in school management.

Teachers may attend training and Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions relative to the importance of understanding the school heads' leadership skills, behaviors, and practices and how significant is teamwork and collaboration in a school-based management system.

Future researchers may replicate this study with different variables and larger sample size to address the limitations of this study. They could explore the investigation with other variables that has significant effect on school heads' performance to give more relevant and concise findings that would enrich our knowledge on school leadership and management.

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

REFERENCES

- 1) Ahmad, S. (2018). Instructional Leadership Practices of Excellent School Principals, from <https://eric.ed.gov/axiv> e-Print Archive Ahmad, M and Rochimah, H. (2021). Improving Teaching Effectiveness Through Transformational Leadership and Integrity. <http://ijereinescore.com> ISSN: 2252-8822, DOI:10.11591
- 2) Akdemir, O. (2020). The Relationship between School Administrators' Transformational Leadership Behaviours and Teachers' Perceptions of Organizational Justice. ISSN:235-2160 African Educational Research Journal
- 3) Ampofo, S., Onyango, G., Ogola, M. (2019). Influence of School Heads' Direct Supervision on Teacher Role Performance in Public Senior High Schools, Central Region, Ghana. IAFOR Journal of Education Volume 7 – Issue 2 – Winter 2019.
- 4) Aquino, C., Afalla, B. and Fabelico, F. (2021). Managing Educational Institutions: School heads' Leadership Practices and Teachers' Performance. ISSN: 2252-8822.DOI:10.11591/ijere.v10i4.21518. <http://ijere.igescore.com>
- 5) Arellano, P. (2021). Management Competencies, Leadership Crisis Practices and Work Commitment Improving School Performances. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1229285.pdf>
- 6) Bantolo, K., Arenga, J. (2021). School Heads' Competencies and School Performance. <https://doi.org/10.79325/IJMRE.20217027976008>.
- 7) Basson, P., Maestry, R. (2019). Collaboration Between School Management and Governing Bodies in Effectively Managing Public Primary School Finances. Vol.39 No. 2. <https://scholar.google.com>.
- 8) Beceril, M., Carcallas, M., Bentillo, J., Omilig, H., Nellas, M., Pacaldo, M., Cabilla, E., Ocba, P. (2022). School Administrators' Leadership Style in the New Normal. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6136856> Vol. 3, Issue 1, pp. 81-92. Bunaiyan, Wala'a and Kelsie McWilliams (2018). A Review of the Literature on Transformational Leadership. Vol. 6, No.1 pp.1-5 International Journal of education, Learning & Development. www.eajournals.org.
- 9) Caingcoy, M. (2021). Competency of School Heads in Leading People Influences School Performance. PRR.21.015. <https://doi.org/10.5739/IJE>
- 10) Campbell, P., Chaseling, M., Boyd, W., Shipway, B. (2018). The Effective Instructional Leader. ISSN: 1941-5257 (Print) 1941-5265 (Online) Journal homepage: <http://www.tandfonline.com/loi/rjie20>.
- 11) Cardona, I., Soria, M., Gumbau, S. (2017). Leadership Intellectual Stimulation and team Learning: The Mediating Role of Team Positive Effect. <https://scholar.google.com>.
- 12) Codilla, L. J. (2022). Management of School-Community Partnership: Basis for Teacher Enhancement Program. International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research, 3(1), 106-110. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.03.01.12>
- 13) Dargantes, M. (2020). Qualities of Leadership Relating to Management Skills of School Heads. SMCC Higher Education Research Journal ISSN Print: 2449-4402 · ISSN Online: 2467-6322 Volume 7. <https://eric.ed.gov/axiv> e-Print Archive
- 14) Digamon, J (2023). Teacher's Organizational Commitment, Citizenship Behavior, Engagement, and Burn-out in the Next Normal: A structural Equation Modeling. Epstein, J. (2016). School, Family, and Community Partnerships (2nd edition). Published 2018 by Routledge 711 Thirs Avenue, New York, NY 0017, USA.
- 15) Fessehatsion, P. (2017). School Principal's Role in Facilitating Change in Teaching-Learning Process: Teachers' Attitude. A Case Study on Five Junior Schools in Asmara, Eritrea. ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.8, No.6, 2017. <https://files.eric.ed.gov>.
- 16) Garcia, S., Rogayan, D. and Gagasa, K. (January 2021). Stakeholders' Awareness and Acceptability of University's Vision and Mission, and Teachers Education Program Goals and Objectives in a state institution in Central Luzon, Philippines. vol.2, No.1, 17-23. <http://dx.doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.02.0.03>.
- 17) Geleta, M. (2015). The Role of School Principal as Instructional Leader. The Case of Shambu Primary School. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
- 18) Gyansah, S., Ogola, M., Guantai, H. (2020). Effect of School Heads' Inspirational Motivation Leadership Practices on Students Academic Achievement in Public High Schools in Kumasi Metropolitan, Ghana. ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.11, No.14, 2020.
- 19) Imoro, I. (April 2018). Assessing the Performance of Heads of Junior High Schools in Tamale Metropolitan. www.udsspace.uds.edu.gh.
- 20) Ingay, A. (January 2018). Leadership Practice and Work Commitment of Elementary School Heads as Determinants of Teachers' Morale in Davao Region. ISSN 2229-5518. International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research. <https://eric.ed.gov/axiv> e-Print Archive
- 21) Jonyo, D., Jonyo, B. (2019). Curriculum Supervision and Implementation in Kenya: The Role of Secondary School Heads. Doi: 10.19044/ejes.v6no2a4 URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.19044/ejes.v6no2a4>

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

- 22) Juhana, J., Wasistiono, S., Tahir, I., & Kusworo. (2020). The Importance of Delegation of Authority, Budget Allocation and Leadership in Improving Performance. *International Journal of Science and Society*, 2(1), 221-228. <https://doi.org/10.54783/ijssoc.v2i1.72>
- 23) Karwanto (2020). The Impact of Covid-19: What School Principals as Instructional leaders Act?. Vol.3 No. 3 ISSN: 2597-4785.<https://scholar.google.com>.
- 24) Kennedy, S., Keino, D. (2017). Effects of Delegation of Authority on Organizational Performance: A case of TWIGA Chemical Industries LTD. <https://scholar.google.com>.
- 25) Khalil, A & Hussain, A. (2021). Transformational Leadership of Head Teachers and Academic Optimism: Perspectives of Teachers in Secondary Schools. Vol. 3, No.2 pp.61-74. *Bulletin of Education and Research*. <https://doaj.orh/>
- 26) Khan, I., Qureshi, Q., Khan. M., Khan, A. (2020). The Integrating Role of Individualized Consideration in Relationship Between Interactional Justice and Employed Performance. Vol. 10 No. 3. *city university Research Journal*
- 27) Kilonzo, J., Mulwa, D. and Kasivu, G. (2020). The Relationship between Principals' Involvement in Developing Teachers and Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Machakos County, Kenya. ISSN 2222-288x Vol. 11, No. 23, 2020. <https://eric.ed.gov/axiv>
- 28) Kongayuy, P. (2020). Delegation of Authority as a Tool for Effective Secondary School Management in the North West Region of Cameroon. Vol.3 No.06. ISSN.2581-5148.<https://scholar.google.com>
- 29) Lasno, A., Saleh, M. (2019). School Principal's Role in the Implementation of School-Based Management for Adiwiyata Program. Vol. 5 No.11. ISSN:2501-1111. <https://scholar.google.com>.
- 30) Limbago, Juyren Lou B., et. al (2020). Personality Traits and Communication Apprehension. *SMCC Teacher Education Journal* ISSN Print: 2008- 0598 • ISSN Online: 2008-0601. Volume 2 • limbago.smccnasipit.edu.ph
- 31) Lingam, G., Lingam, N. and Singh, S. (2021). Instructional Leadership Practices: Teachers Perceptions of a Rural School in Fiji. <https://ro.ecu.edu.au/ajte/vol46/iss6/2>
- 32) Lleras, C. (2005). Path Analysis.<https://www.researchgate.net>
- 33) Mampane, T. (2018). School Heads of Departments' Role in Ensuring Teachers Professional Development in Mathematics. The South African Context. ISSN1314-4693. <https://scholar.google.com>.
- 34) Manafa, I. (2018). Communication Skills Needed by Principals for Effective Management of Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Vol.3 No.2, August 2018, pg.17 –25 (ISSN: 2276 – 9013).
- 35) Matondang, M., Absah, Y., Lubis, A. (2021). The Effect of Trust in Leaders and Communication on Employee Performance Through Motivation Pt. Herfinta Farm and Plantation. ISSN: 2349-9788; P-ISSN: 2454-2237. Vol.8; Issue: 1. www.ijrrjournal.com.
- 36) Montilla, J. E.. (2018). Management Skills of School Administrators and Motivation of Public Elementary School Teachers in Davao City. *Tin-aw*, 2(1). <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=13687>
- 37) Muma, H., Odhiambo, R. (2019). Selected Practices of Delegation used by Principals on Management of Public and Secondary Schools in rachuonyo South Sub-Conty, Kenya. <http://repository.rongovarsity.ac.ke/handle/12356789/2290>.
- 38) Munir, F., Muhammad, A. (2018). Gender Difference in Transformational Leadership Behavior of School Principals and Teachers' Academic Effectiveness. Vol. 4 No.1 pp 99-113.<https://scholar.google.com>. *Bulletin of Education and Research*.
- 39) Muscat, D., Trevena, L., Hayen, A., Shepherd, H. (2019). Skills for shared Decision-Making: Evaluation of a Health Literacy Program for Consumers with Lower Literacy Levels. <https://scholar.google.com>.
- 40) Naidao, D. (2019). Perceptions of Teachers and School Management Teams of the Leadership Roles of Public School Principals. www.eajournals.org
- 41) Nindie, A. (2022). Leadership Management of School Principles; A Case Study of Public Elementary Schools in Bogor Regency. ISSN 2774-8863 Vol. 2, No. 1.
- 42) Ntshoe, I. and Selecho, J. (2014). Investing in Leadership, Governance and Management to Improve Quality of Teaching and Learning: A Human capital perspective. <https://www.scienceopen.com/>
- 43) Nyamubi, G. (2021). The Influence of Heads of Schools' Inspirational Motivation on Teachers' Work Performance. www.ajmse.leena-luna.co.jp. Vol. 10 No.2
- 44) Oco, Richard M. (2022). Leadership Styles of School Heads and Its Relationship to School Performance. *Global Scientific Journals*. EOI: 10.11216/gsj.2022.01.57744
- 45) Patuawa, JM., Sinnema, C.Vivane, R., Tong Zhu. (2022) Addressing Inequality and Underachievement: Intervening to improve middle leaders' problem-solving conversations. *Journal of Educational Change* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-022-09449-3>.

Leadership Skills, Behaviors, And Practices on the Performance of School Heads in Basic Education

- 46) Okoth, Ursulla A. (2018). Transformational Leadership Practices in Curriculum Implementation (Environmental Education) in Secondary Schools in Siaya County, Kenya. doi:10.19044/esj.2018.v14n10p320.
- 47) Ozgenel, Mustafa and Karsantik, Ismail (April, 2020). Effects of School Principals' Leadership Styles on Leadership Practices. Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Sciences. files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/E51251617
- 48) Rahman, M. (2022). Sampling Techniques (Probability) for Qualitative Social Sciences Researches: A Conceptual Guidelines with Examples. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.278/seeur-2022-0023>
- 49) Rehman, A., Khan, M. and Waheed Z. (2019). School Heads' Perceptions About Their Leadership Styles. <https://eric.ed.gov/axiv>
- 50) Rudzani, Israel L. (2017). Ensuring Educational Leadership in the Creation and Leadership of Schools. <https://eric.ed.gov/axiv>
- 51) Sabaruddin, R., Sibilde, I., Bahar, H. (2022). <https://scholar.google.com>. Vol.2 No. 1 ISSN:2503-4413.
- 52) Santos, O., Caparas, L., Roquero, A., et. al (2021). An Assessment of School Leaders' Management of Finances and Resources: Basis for Development Plan. Vol. 2, No. 1, 1085-1094. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1159/ijmaber.02.11.09>.
- 53) Sari, R., Anggreni, S., Rusdinal, N. (2021). Performance Assessment of School Heads in Improving Professionalism in Negri Binaan Basic Schools in Kecamatan Bukit Sundi, Solok District, Indonesia. DOI: 10.46827/ejes.v8i7.3825. ISSN: 2501-1111.
- 54) Sarmago, E. F.. (2019). Analyzing the Communication Styles of Pro-Administration Facebook Pages in Response to Religious, Social, and Political Criticisms. *The PASCHR Journal*, 1(1). <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=14774>
- 55) Sebastian, James, Elaine Allensworth, Wolfgang Wiedermann, Craig Hochbein & Matthew Cunningham (2018). Principal Leadership and School Performance: An Examination of Instructional Leadership and Organizational Management, Leadership and Policy in Schools, DOI: 10.1080/15700763.2018.1513151. <https://eric.ed.gov/axiv>
- 56) Sitanggang, N. (2021). Principals' Interpersonal Skills of Vocational Senior High Schools. DOI 10.4108/eai.31-8-2021.2313723
- 57) Sparks, J. (2021). Understanding Transformational Leadership during a Time of Uncertainty. eric.ed.gov/transformational-leadership.
- 58) Suleman, Q., Ali Syed, M., Shehzad, S., Hussain, I., Khattak, A., Khan, I., Amjid, M. and Khan, I. (2020). Leadership Empowering Behavior as a predictor of Psychological well-being: Evidence from a cross sectional study among secondary school teachers in Kohat Division, Pakistan. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone>.
- 59) Suryanadi, J., Burmansah, Ardianto, H., Poniman (2023). Head School's Performance: Knowledge Management, Organizational Commitment, and transformational leadership as the influencing Factors to Enhance. , Volume 1, 301 – 30
- 60) Thompson, D. (2020). Developing the Personnel Leadership Resources of the Ontario Leading Framework for Principals and vice Principals. <https://eric.ed.gov/axiv>
- 61) Tranmer, M., Murphy, J., Elliot, M. and Pampaka, M. (2020). Multiple Linear Regression (2nd edition). <https://www.csirp.org>.
- 62) Umar, O., Kenayathulia, H and Hoque, K. (2021). Principal Leadership practices and School Effectiveness in Niger State, Nigeria. <https://doi.org/10.15700/saje.v1n3a859>
- 63) Ushoh, E., Lengkong, J., Tambingon, H., Lensun, S (2019). Projecting a Good Image of School: How can a Principal Achieve This Goal?. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 438
- 64) Valenzuela, E., Buenvenida, L (2021). Managing School Operations and Resources in the New Normal and Performance of Public Schools in One School Division in the Philippines. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7237-54992>.
- 65) Villar, R., Yazo, A., Tan, C. Buenvenida, L. and Bandy, M. (2021). School Heads' Leadership Practices in the New Normal, Administrative Disposition and Readiness of the Public Schools in Laguna. ISSN 2684-7167. <http://journals.rsfpres.com/index.php/jtaese>
- 66) Villanueva, A., Disu, S., Villanueva, K. (October 2021). Assessing the School Heads Leadership in the Towns of Nueva Ecija, Philippines: Inter-Relationship of Supervisory Skills, Interpersonal Skills, and Leadership Skills. <https://doi.org/10.423/oalib.1108088>.
- 67) Waruwu, N., Mukhtar, M., Muhab, S. (2021). Principal Authentic Leadership Survey. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 526.
- 68) Wilson, D. B.. (2021). Establishing Indicators for Effective Communication among Task Groups: The Case of the 'Task Force Out of Baguio' (TFOOB). *Southeast Asian Media Studies*, 3(1). <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=16533>
- 69) Yurtseven, R., Akkaş Baysal E., Ocak, G. (2021). Analysis of the relationship between Decision making skills and problem-solving skills of primary school students. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 8(3). 2117-2130. <https://eric.ed.gov/axiv>